

Promoting Autonomous and Critical Reading through Literature Circles: A Case Study in Upper Primary Chinese Education

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Abstract

With the growing emphasis placed on whole-book reading in the latest Chinese curriculum standards, Chinese language instruction in primary schools is undergoing a transition from fragmented text-based teaching to integrated reading approaches. This study explores the implementation and effectiveness of Literature Circles in whole-book reading instruction for upper primary students. Grounded in reader-response theory, social constructivism, and collaborative learning theory, the study designs an instructional model incorporating reading preparation, role-based tasks, group discussion, and outcome presentation. An eight-week teaching experiment was conducted at a primary school in Jinhua, Zhejiang Province. Data collected through classroom observations, student interviews, and textual materials were analyzed to evaluate the teaching effects. The findings suggest that the Literature Circles model significantly enhances students' independent reading skills and critical thinking abilities, while fostering a more democratic, diverse, and engaging classroom environment. To further optimize the integration of Literature Circles into whole-book reading, the study recommends emphasizing student autonomy in text selection, adapting roles to different grade levels and text genres, continuously developing learning tools for routine use, and adopting more flexible teacher roles.

Keywords: Primary Chinese Education; Literature Circles; Whole-Book Reading; Collaborative Learning; Reading Instruction Reform

1. Introduction

In recent years, curriculum reforms in primary Chinese language education have increasingly emphasized the concept of “deep reading”. Among the various instructional approaches aimed at cultivating this competency, whole-book reading has gained significant attention as a means to broaden students' reading horizons and enrich their linguistic experience. Notably, the Compulsory Education Chinese Curriculum Standards (2022 Edition) officially incorporated whole-book reading into the category of “expansive learning tasks.” The standards call for students to “apply diverse strategies to read complete books, share reading reflections through various means, accumulate experience in whole-book reading, and develop sound reading habits.” This shift marks whole-book reading not merely as an extracurricular supplement but as an essential component of classroom-based Chinese instruction.

However, in actual teaching practice, the implementation of whole-book reading faces considerable challenges. Traditional instructional models often rely on teacher-centered explanations with limited student participation, lacking mechanisms for student-led inquiry or collaborative learning. Such approaches make it difficult to stimulate students' interest in reading or cultivate their independent thinking and reading autonomy. Additionally, teachers frequently

report uncertainty about instructional goals and a lack of effective strategies, which complicates the pacing and design of lessons.

Against this backdrop, developing a whole-book reading pedagogy that balances autonomy, interaction, and systematic design has become an urgent issue in contemporary Chinese language education research. Literature Circles, a collaborative reading approach that originated abroad and has recently been introduced into Chinese classrooms, emphasizes small-group collaboration, role-based participation, dialogic engagement, and deep textual construction. It has shown increasing adaptability and effectiveness in the context of Chinese literacy instruction.

This study takes Class 5(3) of B Primary School in Jinhua, Zhejiang Province, as its site of implementation. It explores the integration of the Literature Circles model into whole-book reading instruction, focusing on instructional design, implementation strategies, and pedagogical outcomes. By doing so, the research aims to offer a replicable instructional example for upper primary Chinese language classrooms and reflect on the model's appropriateness and areas for improvement in the context of Chinese language teaching.

2. Literature Review

Conceptual Foundations of Literature Circles

“Literature Circles” is a term that has gained relatively consistent usage in English-language scholarship, sometimes also referred to as book clubs, literature discussions, literature study groups, or discussion circles. The concept was first introduced and promoted by Harvey Daniels as a form of collaborative literary reading. In this model, a small group of students gathers to engage in in-depth discussions around a literary text, with each member assuming a specific role and responsibility. Students typically read the assigned text independently while preparing their role-based tasks, and then convene as a group to share their insights. The discussion is guided not by a teacher's list of predetermined questions but by the students' own responses to the text.

This study adopts the same conceptualization of “Literature Circles”, emphasizing a cooperative and inquiry-based reading process. While this model has long been practiced in classrooms abroad, it has only recently begun to gain traction in Chinese reading instruction. Many frontline teachers in China are already familiar with forms of group discussions or class-wide book clubs, but Literature Circles differ from traditional reading groups. Whereas traditional reading groups often emphasize textual analysis and the pursuit of correct interpretation, Literature Circles frame reading as an interactive process. Drawing on Rosenblatt's (1978) reader-response theory, they position meaning-making as a dynamic exchange: readers construct understanding through personal engagement with the text and through sharing individual interpretations shaped by lived experience.

The goal of Literature Circles is not to derive a single, “correct” interpretation of a text, but rather to recognize that meaning emerges through dialogue and collaboration. In facilitating such discussions, teachers are encouraged to view Literature Circles as a way to foster critical thinking and student connection, rather than solely focusing on reading strategies or textual analysis.

Research on the Implementation of Literature Circles

The implementation of Literature Circles involves assigning specific roles to each group member to ensure effective collaboration and discussion. In this process, students lead the discussions, while the teacher assumes the role of facilitator or mediator. The implementation typically follows four main stages: selecting reading materials, building community, preparing for discussion, and conducting the discussion and sharing.

Selection of Reading Materials. The choice of reading materials plays a crucial role in fostering meaningful discussions within Literature Circles. According to Brabham and Villaume (2000), novels are the most commonly used genre, although other types of texts—such as nonfiction, picture books, or newspaper articles—can also be successfully incorporated.

Scholars such as Farinacci (2008) and Peralta-Nash and Dutch (2000) suggest that texts for Literature Circles should meet several criteria: they should accommodate a range of reading levels and interests, reflect students' linguistic needs and abilities, relate to their lived experiences, and stimulate critical reflection and discussion. After students select the texts they wish to read, Literature Circles can be formed based on shared reading interests or chosen book titles.

Building Community. One of the key purposes of Literature Circles is to foster a classroom community in which students and teachers engage in mutual learning and exchange (King, 2001). For students who are new to the model, teachers may need to establish clear guidelines to support community-building and help students understand the importance of collaborative learning (Gilbert, 2000). Farinacci (2008) recommends that teachers initiate discussions with students on topics such as:

- (1) how to handle unfamiliar words;
- (2) how to respond constructively to group members;
- (3) how to identify discussion-worthy ideas; and
- (4) how to maintain respectful and productive group dynamics.

These conversations help students gradually develop a shared understanding of how Literature Circles function as collaborative learning communities.

Discussion Preparation. Students must not only be familiar with the reading material but also be ready to fulfill their assigned roles during discussion. Common roles include Discussion Director, Illustrator, Passage Finder, and Connector (Daniels, 2002). Each student receives a role sheet outlining their specific responsibilities. Prior to the discussion, students are expected to complete their individual tasks, then share and exchange their perspectives with the group. Alternatively, students may record their reactions, thoughts, questions, or points of confusion about the text (Brabham & Villaume, 2000; Farinacci, 1998; Peralta-Nash & Dutch, 2000; Burns, 1998).

Discussion and Sharing. In every Literature Circle, students are given time and space to articulate their interpretations and respond to their peers through thoughtful dialogue. Groups are formed based on students' reading interests or selected books (Peralta-Nash & Dutch, 2000). Once all members have completed their reading plans and role assignments, they gather to begin their discussion, using their notes and role sheets as a guide.

For students with limited experience in Literature Circles, teachers may need to model appropriate discussion behaviors, such as offering reflective responses, giving respectful feedback, and practicing active listening and inquiry. Once students have internalized the norms and skills of discussion, the teacher can gradually step back and allow students to take ownership of the process.

The Educational Value of Whole-Book Reading

Given the increasing emphasis on deep reading in literacy education, many researchers have explored the educational value of whole-book reading. These studies primarily focus on its contributions to student knowledge acquisition, reading literacy, and curriculum reform in Chinese language education.

First, whole-book reading can effectively stimulate students' interest in reading and improve their overall reading competence. Compared to excerpt-based or single-passage readings found in textbooks, whole-book reading requires sustained engagement with longer texts, richer content, and more complex structures. This places higher demands on students' ability to concentrate, identify problems, process information, reason analytically, and solve problems. Only when students are equipped with strategies for whole-book reading and understand its purpose can they truly appreciate the pleasure of reading and develop lasting habits. In this regard, whole-book reading helps to foster positive reading habits, enhance language proficiency, and cultivate thoughtful readers.

Second, whole-book reading promotes the development of higher-order thinking skills by encouraging more comprehensive and reflective engagement with texts. According to Guan Shuwen and colleagues, whole-book reading not only increases reading volume and depth, but also allows students to move from superficial to deeper levels of reading, thus advancing their reading competence and critical thinking. Compared with single-text readings, whole-book reading involves greater narrative complexity and thematic depth. Students must grasp the storyline as a whole, summarize key content and themes, and construct personal interpretations—all of which strengthen their independence and critical reasoning, and cultivate a spirit of rational inquiry.

Third, whole-book reading encourages students to become self-directed learners through sustained engagement. Unlike short texts, which can be handled with a limited set of reading strategies, whole-book reading often requires students to use a range of techniques—including skimming, scanning, selective reading, and close reading—based on their purpose. In doing so, students develop and refine their own learning strategies. Additionally, the challenges and uncertainties encountered in reading full-length texts encourage learners to think actively, seek solutions, and gain satisfaction from problem-solving. Over time, students gradually evolve into autonomous, reflective learners.

Instructional Strategies for Whole-Book Reading

International research on whole-book reading has long emphasized both its importance and instructional methods. For instance, Jim Trelease, a renowned expert on children's reading, highlighted the significance of read-alouds in *The Read-Aloud Handbook*. He also advocated for sustained silent reading (SSR) as a key method. In France, the National Curriculum Guide for High School Chinese recommends that students read at least one high-quality literary work per month and encourages the reading of classics, novels, and biographies from a young age. Internationally, therefore, whole-book reading is commonly linked to literary value, student choice, and instructional design.

In China, research on whole-book reading has grown since the concept entered classroom instruction. Most studies focus on specific instructional strategies and implementation methods. For example, some educators have promoted class book clubs as effective reading activities. Ye Xuebing argued that class-based book clubs are a practical and engaging way to support whole-book reading. Yan Lei emphasized the use of mind maps to help students analyze thematic issues and review key points of the text, thereby improving comprehension and memory. Other researchers, such as Li Wenliang, have explored the use of reading journals to integrate reading with writing, making reading logs a valuable pedagogical tool. These practices reflect growing attention to instructional diversity, student-centered approaches, and deeper engagement with literary texts.

Overall, research on whole-book reading in China highlights the need for carefully selected materials, diversified methods, and active student participation. Emphasis is placed on processes such as organizing, discussing, and collaborating, with the goal of connecting reading to students' everyday lives and promoting their agency as readers.

3. Current Study

To date, a considerable body of research has explored whole-book reading and related instructional strategies. However, several limitations remain:

First, existing studies often lack coherence and systematic frameworks. While many valuable classroom practices and lesson plans have been developed, few efforts have synthesized these practices into a comprehensive theoretical or pedagogical system. Research tends to focus on isolated cases rather than overarching principles. Moreover, little attention has been paid to how students internalize and apply whole-book reading strategies in actual classroom settings.

Second, the scope of current research is limited in terms of target populations. Many studies concentrate on middle and high school students, while fewer address whole-book reading in the upper primary grades. Yet, the 2022 curriculum standards explicitly call for whole-book reading at the upper primary level. Additionally, most studies emphasize enhancing student motivation, while offering less detailed guidance on how teachers can effectively support and scaffold reading.

Third, there is a notable lack of practical experience and research on integrating Literature Circles into whole-book reading. Although many scholars recognize the compatibility and potential effectiveness of Literature Circles in this context, the approach has not been widely implemented or studied in Chinese classrooms. Key issues—such as aligning the model with national curriculum content, integrating it with traditional reading pedagogy, and adapting it to Chinese classroom culture—remain underexplored.

In response, this study draws on both domestic and international research to examine how the Literature Circles model can be effectively integrated into whole-book reading instruction in Chinese primary schools. Specifically, the study aims to (1) clarify the theoretical foundations of Literature Circles and whole-book reading; (2) evaluate the pedagogical value and contextual relevance of the model; and (3) investigate its practical implementation and outcomes through empirical classroom research.

4. Method

This study adopts a research approach that integrates theoretical inquiry with classroom-based practical application. It draws upon established educational theories while grounding its analysis in real-world teaching practices. The aim is to investigate how Literature Circles can be effectively applied to whole-book reading instruction in upper primary Chinese language classrooms. The research process is structured into four key phases:

Literature Review and Problem Identification

The study begins with an extensive review of existing literature to identify key challenges in the current practice of whole-book reading instruction. This review highlights common issues such as limited student engagement, lack of effective instructional models, and insufficient teacher guidance, thereby helping to determine the central focus and objectives of the research.

Theoretical Framework Construction

To address the identified problems, the study builds a theoretical foundation centered on two core concepts: whole-book reading and Literature Circles. It analyzes the theoretical underpinnings, pedagogical features, and instructional

value of Literature Circles, particularly in relation to their compatibility with the goals of upper primary reading instruction. This theoretical groundwork informs the design of the classroom intervention.

Instructional Design and Classroom Implementation

Based on the theoretical framework and an analysis of students' learning needs, the study develops a three-phase instructional intervention. This intervention is implemented in an upper primary classroom, with a focus on integrating Literature Circles into whole-book reading activities. Throughout the teaching process, instructional strategies are continuously refined through reflective observation and iterative improvement. The goal is to identify effective implementation pathways and optimize the teaching model.

Data Collection and Evaluation

During the intervention, various forms of process-oriented data are collected and analyzed to evaluate the outcomes of the teaching experiment. These include classroom observation notes, student work samples, role sheets, reading journals, self- and peer-evaluation forms, and post-lesson interviews. The analysis assesses the impact of the Literature Circles model on students' reading engagement, autonomy, collaborative skills, and critical thinking. Based on these findings, the study identifies effective practices, highlights implementation challenges, and offers evidence-based recommendations to guide future teaching.

By systematically integrating theoretical analysis with practical experimentation, this study aims to offer a pedagogically sound and contextually appropriate model for using Literature Circles to enhance whole-book reading instruction in Chinese primary schools. It also seeks to provide teachers with actionable strategies and insights for fostering student-centered, inquiry-based literacy learning.

5. Results

Following nearly three months of classroom-based instructional intervention, the study systematically analyzed data collected from diagnostic, formative, and summative assessments. The findings demonstrate that incorporating Literature Circles into whole-book reading instruction significantly enhances students' independent reading capabilities, critical thinking skills, and social-emotional development. The classroom atmosphere also became more democratic, inclusive, and engaging. Meanwhile, challenges encountered during implementation were identified, prompting reflective insights and suggestions for future improvement.

Strengthening Independent Reading Skills

Guided by the principle of "teaching for independence," the primary instructional goal was to cultivate students' capacity for autonomous reading. Students gradually demonstrated greater independence in their reading process, relying less on external assistance and more on internalized strategies to complete group reading and discussion tasks effectively.

Tools such as reading journals and role sheets played a key role in scaffolding independent learning. These tools transformed internal thought processes into visible artifacts, enabling students to externalize their comprehension and critical engagement. For example, the Passage Finder role required students to select notable excerpts from the book and explain their significance, fostering close reading and evidence-based thinking. Over time, students became more adept at using these tools and even began to move beyond them, indicating the development of internalized reading strategies.

Improved individual reading skills also contributed to more effective group discussions. In the early stages of the intervention, students often struggled with off-topic conversations or disorganized participation. Some students failed to complete role tasks, which hindered group progress. However, with repeated practice, teacher guidance, and peer support, students developed greater confidence and responsibility. As one student reflected:

“At first, I wasn’t sure how to complete my role sheet or express my opinions. But after several rounds of discussion, I realized that everyone was very accepting. It started to feel more like chatting with friends, so I became more comfortable participating.”

Classroom observations and student self-assessments confirmed these improvements. Students’ role sheets became increasingly complete, logical, and insightful. Some students began to expand their responsibilities by preparing for other roles in addition to their assigned ones. In post-lesson reflections, 31 students reported having completed their role tasks independently, and 27 stated that they were able to justify their viewpoints with valid reasons. These findings indicate that students not only mastered the tools of Literature Circles but also developed habits of independent reading and critical engagement.

In addition, students were given opportunities for creative expression. Through dramatizations, story rewrites, and stylistic imitations, they demonstrated a solid understanding of character development and textual style. These activities allowed students to deepen their comprehension through embodied and imaginative practices, thus enhancing reading motivation and interpretive depth.

Deepening Critical Thinking

At the outset of the Literature Circles activities, students primarily focused on completing role sheets in a perfunctory manner, treating the process as routine homework. As the project progressed, however, students began to respond to each other’s ideas, question interpretations, and offer alternative perspectives—signaling the emergence of genuine critical dialogue.

Educational research supports the notion that learning evolves along a continuum from passive reception to interactive construction. According to Professor Sheng Qunli, learning depth increases with engagement level: passive learning yields surface knowledge; active learning fosters knowledge integration; constructive learning enables independent reasoning; interactive learning promotes collaborative inquiry and innovation.

In traditional reading instruction, students often remain passive, simply absorbing information. Literature Circles transform this by creating a socially interactive learning environment that encourages students to ask “why” and “how,” to critique ideas, and to engage in reflective reasoning.

As one student shared: *“When someone said this part showed how lively the bird paradise was, I immediately thought of another sentence that did too. Listening to others made me think of more things to add—or even to disagree with.”*

This kind of interaction enriched the interpretive process. Students’ role sheets reflected increasing diversity in interpretive angles, and during interviews, many students expressed excitement about encountering new perspectives from peers. Through such dialogic exchanges, students co-constructed understanding, exercised evaluative judgment, and matured as critical readers.

Fostering a Collaborative Reading Community

Literature Circles are inherently social in nature, requiring all group members to participate, listen actively, and prepare to speak. This collaborative format stimulated students' communication, cooperation, and mutual support.

Observation records indicated an increase in participation and enthusiasm over time. The shared responsibility embedded in role assignments encouraged students to be accountable to the group. Students learned to appreciate diverse viewpoints, support one another, and engage respectfully.

For example, one student said: *"I feel more responsible now because my role matters to the group. When I complete my task well, I feel accomplished."*

Another reflected: *"In the beginning, one boy in our group rarely participated. But since we started using roles, he became more engaged because without his part, the group couldn't function."*

This sense of interdependence promoted deeper social-emotional development. The democratic and inclusive classroom atmosphere allowed even previously reserved students to voice their thoughts confidently. Students also developed a stronger sense of empathy, appreciation for group contributions, and pride in collective achievement.

As one student noted:

"I really like the 'group gratitude form' because it lets us recognize each person's strengths. Everyone is important."

Through sustained collaboration and shared inquiry, students not only enhanced their reading and thinking skills but also formed a learning community characterized by respect, cooperation, and mutual encouragement.

6. Discussion

Research limitations

The integration of Literature Circles into whole-book reading instruction represents a pedagogical innovation that departs from conventional reading models in Chinese language classrooms. It differs in terms of text selection, classroom leadership dynamics, instructional methods, assessment approaches, and student role design. In an effort to further improve the quality of whole-book reading instruction grounded in Literature Circles, this study reflects on the key challenges encountered during implementation and offers practical recommendations for refinement.

Limited Flexibility in Text Selection

In this study, the majority of reading materials were selected based on the fifth-grade textbook, leaving little room for variation or student autonomy. By the end of the intervention, some students expressed a desire to read different books in smaller groups, citing fatigue from reading a single title throughout the project. In fact, the only lesson that offered students the freedom to choose specific chapters was the one based on Selected Essays of Ba Jin.

While it may be pedagogically sound for teachers to select texts in the early stages of implementation, this top-down approach may limit student motivation in the long term. These findings highlight the need to expand text selection strategies to include more diverse and student-driven options.

Rigid Role Design

Although the role-based structure of Literature Circles proved effective with fifth-grade students—many of whom quickly mastered and even began rotating roles—the same structure may not suit students in higher or lower grades. For instance, the role of Word Wizard, which focuses on vocabulary clarification, may become redundant for older students with stronger language skills. Conversely, roles such as Discussion Director may prove too demanding for younger students, potentially discouraging participation at the outset.

To adapt the model more effectively, roles should be tailored to developmental stages. More creative roles like Illustrator may better engage younger learners.

Additionally, different literary genres require different interpretive approaches. Role design should reflect these genre-specific features. For example, narratives may benefit from character-focused roles, while expository texts may require roles emphasizing structure or argumentation. The role sheets themselves should also evolve with students' cognitive levels—for example, incorporating higher-order thinking prompts or guided evidence statements.

Limited Instructional Experience of the Researcher

The success of this study owed much to the inherent appeal of Literature Circles, which kept students engaged and motivated. Nonetheless, the researcher acknowledges limitations in classroom experience and text mastery. In some cases, insufficient content knowledge hindered the ability to guide students toward deeper thematic insights.

A key premise of Literature Circles is that students assume greater ownership of their learning. However, this does not imply the teacher's withdrawal from instruction. Rather, the teacher plays a vital role in providing timely scaffolding—monitoring the quality of group dialogue, the depth of student thinking, and the classroom dynamics. During whole-class sharing, the teacher must also synthesize discussions, highlight key language features, and affirm students' critical contributions.

Each stage of Literature Circles poses distinct instructional demands. In the early phases, teachers must actively motivate and model appropriate discourse. Later on, they must discreetly manage pacing, refocus distracted students, and adjust time allocations. In this study, the teacher's guidance was not always sufficiently responsive to classroom contingencies, and some instructional goals were only partially achieved.

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